

Control strategy of stable discharge of mechanical energy storage through piston expander in micro compressed air energy storage

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KEYWORDS

CAES, Piston Expander, Control strategy

ABSTRACT

The development of highly efficient long-term electricity storage technology is of great interest to scientists and engineers, particularly due to the inflexibility of renewable energy sources regarding key parameters that need to be maintained in the energy system. One such electricity storage technology is compressed air energy storage (CAES), which enables long-term energy storage with flexible capacity and rated power size. However, one of the main challenges hindering the advancement of this technology is its efficiency and high investment costs, especially for small and micro installations up to 1 MW. Traditional control methods require the use of pressure reducers, resulting in energy losses due to pressure drops in the compressed air tank during the unloading process. Nonetheless, a stable and highly efficient control algorithm for air storage discharge remains elusive. In this study, we investigate a control algorithm that considers the constant air energy provided into the piston chamber. Our proposed algorithm dynamically adjusts the width and pulse of the portion of compressed air based on pressure signals in the compressed storage tank and the position of the piston. We estimate that the efficiency of converting the mechanical energy of compressed air into electrical energy in the piston expander may reach as high as 70-80%.

INTRODUCTION

The initiative of the “European Green Deal,” the climate and energy policy framework in the “fit-for-5” climate package, and the Strategic Energy Technology Plan introduce stringent requirements for the energy sector, focusing on climate neutrality, environmental protection, and sustainable management of natural resources. This compels significant energy transformation in the EU, emphasizing the utilization of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) while maintaining stability and security of electricity supply (Saadat et al., 2015). Consequently, there is a pressing need to enhance the energy sector by introducing new energy storage technologies on both large and small scales, addressing both short and long-term requirements (Mitali et al., 2022). Presently, electrochemical methods, particularly Li-ion batteries, are predominantly used for electricity storage due to their high efficiency and stability (Olabi et al., 2020). However, this technology exhibits limitations such as short work cycles (4-8 hours), limited service life (7-10 years), self-discharge, capacity degradation, finite resources, and adverse environmental impact (Nitta et al., 2015). Therefore, there is a growing interest in alternative energy storage technologies, particularly those with longer cycle times exceeding 4-8 hours. One such technology is Compressed Air Energy Storage (CAES), where air is compressed during charging and stored in a mechanical energy tank (such as a cavern) and subsequently expanded in an expander during discharge (Budt et al., 2016). The efficiency of CAES technology typically ranges from 40-50% for small installations (Ma et al., 2020) to 60% for large installations (Barbour et al., 2021).

Given the current state of knowledge, both scientists and engineers have identified significant barriers and limitations in the development of small-scale CAES systems, particularly concerning unstable electricity generation, pressure fluctuations, and energy losses during the discharge of mechanical energy storage. These challenges stem from the nature of the charging and discharging process, which involves both exo- and endo-thermal reactions, ultimately impacting the overall efficiency of the storage process (often not exceeding 50%). The majority of CAES solutions

documented in the literature rely on air expansion in turbines, which, while effective for large-scale installations, suffer from low operating point controllability, making them unsuitable for smaller-scale implementations (Courtois et al., 2021). Large-volume geological or mining facilities are typically used for storing air, with pressure fluctuations mitigated by maintaining air at constant pressure (Ebrahimi et al., 2019). However, this approach is prohibitively expensive, complex, and impractical for classic CAES pressure vessels on a smaller scale. Existing small-scale CAES installations primarily exist in laboratory settings and predominantly utilize turbines (Maia et al., 2016; Vladuca et al., 2020) or, less commonly, piston expanders (Bollinger, 2015). Pressure reducers are often employed to stabilize pressure during discharge, yet this results in significant energy losses from the mechanical energy reservoir and contributes to the overall inefficiency of the storage process.

The paper presents the possibility of dynamically cutting off the compressed air supply to the piston expander when unloading mechanical energy storage, depending on the pressure in the air tank and the expected power, instead of using a pressure regulator. In order to achieve a stable and highly effective process, the mechanical energy reservoir is discharged. On the basis of computer simulations of the mathematical model of the piston expander, the relationship between the air supply cut off and the pressure in the tank for constant power on the expander shaft is presented.

METHODS

The Compressed Air Energy Storage (CAES) system comprises fundamental components: a compressor, a tank, and an expander. In Figure 1, a micro-CAES setup with three piston expanders is depicted. Each piston expander is equipped with three cylinders and a set of controllable valves, allowing for three independent states: supply, venting, and cut-off for each chamber. Furthermore, the expander operation controller sends appropriate signals to the control valves based on pressure signals from the tank (p_s) and the positions of the pistons (x_1, x_2, x_3).

Figure 1: Compressed air energy storage system with piston expander.

Mathematical Model

The briefly mathematical model of the dynamics of air expansion in the piston expander and energy conversion into mechanical energy on the shaft is presented below. The model is described in detail and experimentally validated in (Leszczynski et al., 2023). The mathematical model is based on the differential equation of moments on the crankshaft (1) in accordance with the second law of dynamics:

$$J \frac{d^2 \alpha}{dt^2} = T + T_b + T_l \quad (1)$$

where: J is total moment of inertia of all elements in motion, α is angular position of crank, t is time, T_b is resistive torque in bearings, T_l is load torque and T is driving torque from cylinder. The driving torque is written as the sum of the torque from each cylinder i due to the force of the generated by it F_i and the angular position of the crank α_i :

$$T = \sum_{i=1}^3 r \cdot F_i \sin(\alpha_i) \left(\left(\frac{r}{l} \right)^2 \sin^2(\alpha_i) + \frac{r}{l} \cos(\alpha_i) \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{r}{l} \right)^2 \sin^2(\alpha_i)} - 1 \right) \quad (2)$$

where: r is the crank length and l is the connection rod length. The force generated by each cylinder i is the result of compressed air acting on the piston and Columbus-viscous friction force with Stribeck effect $F_{i,fr}$.

$$F_i = A_{i,1}(p_{i,1} - p_{i,2}) - A_{i,2}p_0 + F_{i,fr} \quad (3)$$

where: $p_{i,1}$, $p_{i,2}$ are pressure at both side of piston, respectively, $A_{i,1}$ is piston cross section, $A_{i,2}$ is cross-sectional area of the piston minus the piston rod and p_0 is ambient pressure. The pressure of both chambers of the cylinder is calculated by Clapeyron equation $p = \frac{RT_j m_j}{V_j}$, where: R is the individual gas constant for air, T is the temperature, m is the air mass, and V is the volume for each chamber. Mechanical power is determined from the product of the driving torque T and the angular velocity.

$$P = T\omega = T \frac{d\alpha}{dt} \quad (4)$$

The efficiency of converting compressed air energy into mechanical energy on the shaft is determined as the ratio of shaft power to air power according to (Cai et al., 2002):

$$\eta = \frac{P}{p_s V \ln \frac{p_s}{p_0}} \quad (5)$$

The cut off ratio CFR is defined as the ratio of the position of the piston of the cylinder at which power is cut off x_{CF} to stroke s .

$$CFR = \frac{x_{CF}}{s} \quad (6)$$

The valve control signal VCS is then defined based on CFR as $VCS = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } x < x_{CF} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$.

Computational setup

To determine the correlation between tank pressure and the cut-off signal (CFS), a series of computer simulations were conducted to analyze the operating characteristics of the expander. The simulations were based on a mathematical model represented by a set of ordinary differential equations with variable coefficients, which were solved using the Runge-Kutta-Fehlberg method with a fixed step. The mathematical model was implemented using MATLAB syntax. The simulations covered various pressures ranging from 3 to 12 bar and cut-off signals (CFS) ranging from 0.06 to 0.6. The parameters of the simulated system are outlined in Table 1. Based on the simulation results, the data points were approximated to determine functions that describe the relationships between the analyzed parameters

Table 1: System and construction parameters of simulated installations.

Parameter	Value
Supply pressure	{3,4,6,8,9,10,12} bar
Cut-off signals	{0.06, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6}
Torque load	{0 – 1600} Nm
Piston diameter	3x100 mm
Piston stroke	500 mm
Cylinder port size	G1
Crank length	250 mm
Connection rod length	1 m

RESULTS

Figure 2 shows the general dependencies of mechanical power and efficiency on the angular velocity (load) for various pressures (6, 8, 12 bar) for $CFS = 0.2$.

Figure 2: Operational characteristics of the piston expander: a) Mechanical power; b) Efficiency.

The primary objective of expander operation is to maximize conversion efficiency, which is achieved within a rotational speed range of 0-100 rpm, specifically narrowed to 30-80 rpm. Within this range, efficiency typically ranges between 70-80%, with mechanical power output ranging from 1 to 3 kW, depending on the pressure. For the simulations, we will concentrate on the expander operating point at a speed of 50 rpm. Figure 3 illustrates the computational results of mechanical power and efficiency for a piston expander operating at a speed of 50 rpm, varying with CFR and supply pressure. Mechanical power increases with supply pressure and CFR , whereas efficiency decreases inversely with increase in supply pressure and CFR .

Figure 3: The influence of supplied pressure and cut-off ratio CFR in piston expander on: a) Mechanical Power; b) Efficiency.

Figure 4: The influence of the cut-off ratio CFR on the dependence of the supply pressure on: a) Mechanical Power; b) Efficiency.

Figure 3b illustrates a specific operational region where efficiency remains consistently high, ranging between 70-80%, across the entire pressure range and *CFR* values from 0 to 0.4. Additionally, distinct planes of constant power are evident, running parallel to the plane defined by the pressure signal and *CFR*. This operational region allows for precise control of the expander's parameters to achieve both constant power output and high efficiency. In Figure 4a, a series of curves representing mechanical power versus supply pressure for different *CFR* values is presented. Linear approximations were applied to the data points. It's worth noting that the minimum *CFR* value considered in the simulations was 0.06, as the expander did not initiate operations below this threshold. From the chart, it is deduced that specific *CFR* values can be assigned to maintain a constant power output within the range of 1-3 kW, allowing for the adjustment of air expansion by varying the *CFR* value in response to changes in pressure. Moreover, Figure 4b demonstrates that efficiency remains consistently high, ranging between 70-80%, for all *CFR* values up to a pressure of 6 bar

Figure 5: Dependence of the cut-off ratio *CFR* on the supply pressure for constant mechanical power of the piston expander.

However, it is notable that efficiency begins to decrease above 8 bar for *CFR* values of 0.4, and above 10 bar for *CFR* values of 0.3. Figure 4a facilitated the identification of supply pressure and *CFR* points corresponding to constant power levels of 1.5, 2, 2.5, and 3 kW, as depicted in Figure 5. These points of constant mechanical power were approximated using power functions.

DISCUSSION

The relationship between *CFR* and supplied pressure was determined empirically, following an empirical dependence expressed by the formula $CFR = a \cdot p_s^b$, where *a* and *b* are coefficients determined by specific design and process parameters. The coefficient *b* of this function can be assumed constant for a given rotational speed, typically taking a value of $b = 2.2$. However, the coefficient *a* varies depending on the mechanical power. It is important to note that the coefficient *a* should have dimensions of $[1 / \text{Pa}]$ to ensure *CFR* remains dimensionless. Therefore, it is hypothesized that a semi-empirical formula can be derived:

$$CFR = \left(c \frac{As\omega}{P} \right)^{-2.2} \cdot p_s^{-2.2} \quad (7)$$

where: *A* is the cross section of the piston, *s* is the stroke of the piston, ω is the angular speed, *P* is the mechanical power and *c* is the empirical coefficient. However, this function (7) requires further analysis and testing.

The dynamic adjustment of the *CFR* cutoff ratio enables the continuous supply of constant air power to the actuator, ensuring stable generation of mechanical power with high efficiency. Implementing such a function in the air expander eliminates the need for additional pressure regulators during discharge, maintaining an efficiency range of 70-80%. However, modifying the power output from the expander is possible to some extent, albeit with a decrease in efficiency as power increases. Furthermore, there are certain limitations to the application of this function. In practice, it was observed that the *CFR* could not be lowered below 0.06 in the data obtained from computer simulations. Below this threshold, the expander did not activate, likely due to insufficient force for the piston to initiate movement, possibly

influenced by dead volumes or inflow velocity. On the other hand, the upper limit of the CFR value varies depending on the mechanical power. Generally, above 0.4 and 0.5 for high pressures, the overall efficiency of the system drops below 70%. For instance, for power levels of 1.5 kW, the maximum CFR value is up to 4 bar, while for 2 kW, it is approximately 5 bar. This maximum pressure limit increases with mechanical power, albeit at the expense of reduced operating capacity of the air tank. Despite these limitations, this method demonstrates significant potential for application in air piston expanders within CAES systems.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a method to control the discharge of a compressed air tank by a piston expander, which is characterised by the stability of the generated power and the high efficiency of energy conversion. The control algorithm is based on a dynamic modification of the cutoff ratio parameter, defined as the ratio of the piston position at the moment of power cut-off to the stroke. This results in a variable-width pulse feed. The empirical dependence of the supply pressure on CFR was determined on the basis of a power function, and the further direction of unification of this function was indicated. It is estimated that the tank discharge efficiency in this method may be at least 70-80%. The initial limits and barriers to this method were identified. Further research will involve further tests and verification of the created algorithm. Its implementation and verification are planned in a mathematical model and computer simulations. Then, it is planned to perform experimental verification on a test stand. Additionally, further work will be done to unify this relationship and develop its modifications.

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REFERENCES

- Barbour, E.R., D.L. Pottie and P. Eames. 2021. "Why is adiabatic compressed air energy storage yet to become a viable energy storage option?". *iScience*, no. 24, 1–26.
- Bollinger, B. 2015. "Demonstration of Isothermal Compressed Air Energy Storage to Support Renewable Energy Production". *SustainX Smart Grid Program*, 1–49.
- Budt, M., D. Wolf, R. Span and J. Yan. 2016. "A review on compressed air energy storage: Basic principles, past milestones and recent developments". *Applied Energy*, no. 170, 250–268.
- Cai, M., T. Kagawa and K. Kawashima. 2002. "Energy Conversion Mechanics and Power Evaluation of Compressible Fluid in Pneumatic Actuator Systems". *37th Intersociety Energy Conversion Engineering Conference (IECEC)*, 471–474.
- Courtois, N., M. Najafiyazdi, R. Lotfalian, R. Boudreault and M. Picard. 2021. "Analytical expression for the evaluation of multi-stage adiabatic-compressed air energy storage (A-CAES) systems cycle efficiency". *Applied Energy*, no. 288, 116592.
- Ebrahimi, M., R. Cariveau, D.S.K. Ting and A. McGillis. 2019. "Conventional and advanced exergy analysis of a grid connected underwater compressed air energy storage facility". *Applied Energy*, no. 242, 1198–1208.
- Leszczyński, J.S., D. Gryboś and J. Markowski. 2023. "Analysis of optimal expansion dynamics in a reciprocating drive for a micro-CAES production system". *Applied Energy*, no. 350, 121742.
- Ma, X., C. Zhang, K. Li, F. Li, H. Wang and J. Chen. 2020. "Optimal dispatching strategy of regional micro energy system with compressed air energy storage". no. 212.
- Maia, T.A.C., J.E.M. Barros, B.J. Cardoso Filho and M.P. Porto. 2016. "Experimental performance of a low cost micro-CAES generation system". *Applied Energy*, no. 182, 358–364.
- Mitali, J., S. Dhinakaran and A.A. Mohamad. 2022. "Energy storage systems: a review". *Energy Storage and Saving*, no. 1, 166–216.
- Nitta, N., F. Wu, J.T. Lee and G. Yushin. 2015. "Li-ion battery materials: present and future". *Materials Today*, no. 18, 252–264.
- Olabi, A.G., T. Wilberforce, M. Ramadan, M.A. Abdelkareem and A.H. Alami. 2020. "Compressed air energy storage systems: Components and operating parameters – A review". *Journal of Energy Storage*, no. 34, 1–24.
- Saadat, M., F.A. Shirazi and P.Y. Li. 2015. "Modeling and control of an open accumulator Compressed Air Energy Storage (CAES) system for wind turbines". *Applied Energy*, no. 137, 603–616.

Vladuca, I., C. Borzea, D. Ionescu, A. Aranu, R. Ciobanu, V. Ringheanu and R. Nedelcu. 2020. "Compressed air energy storage facility with water tank for thermal recovery". E3S Web of Conferences, no. 180, 1–10.